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Study on the Work Life of Fisher folks in Thota Bengre Fishing Community in Coastal Mangaluru

Pradeep M.D*

*Research Scholar, School of Law, Alliance University, Bengaluru & Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

Abstract

Labour is the prime contributor for the industrial growth and economic development of a country. It is known to be the segment which contributes significantly to the GDP of the Nation. Work is generally known to be the physical or mental engagement of the people in any economically productive activity for their livelihood. The Indian economy is characterized by the existence of a vast majority of employment in the unorganised sectors. Its dominance in the employment front is such that more than 90 per cent of the total workforce belongs to the informal economy. Planned Economic Development in the country can be achieved by eliminating poverty through employment and income generation. In this regard, Fisheries sector plays an important role in the developing countries of the world. The fisheries contribution to the Indian economy has enriched after the introduction of advanced technology to increase the yield per unit area of water attracting more foreign exchange. The problems of poverty and malnutrition faced in coastal areas can be simultaneously met through, planned utilization of available local resources and encouraging participation of the local people in the fishing occupation. Fisher folk are those people who engage in fishing activities. They are the victims of economic oppression and lives under social prejudices with low social status. There is a need to undertake systematic study on the life of the fishermen to seek solutions to their existing problems and to improve their overall status. This study will review into the work life of fisher folks in Thota Bengre village belonging to Mangaluru taluk in Karnataka State.

Keywords: Labour, Employment, Income, Fisher Folk, Status, Work Life.

Introduction

Unorganised sector is considered to be the great contributor to the Indian economy, therefore, it is important to conduct extensive investigation upon the employment relationship and working conditions by considering types of occupation, regulatory mechanisms, share of contribution, challenges faced by the labourers etc.[1]. Fisheries sector is highly productive with nutritious food, employment and export earning which stimulates the economic growth in the country. India has set a milestone by becoming second largest fish producing country in the world by recording 11.41 million tonnes productivity during 2016-17. The Fisheries Department constituted a fish breeding centre at Pilikula. The development of fisheries are hindered by the lack of landing facility, auction yard, water supply, drainage, electricity, ice plant and cold storage and other factors including prevalence of middlemen, over exploitation of inshore fishing, encroachment of offshore fishing by the enterprises. The regulations like The Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) Act prohibiting development activity within 200 meters from high tide line on the landward side and 100 meters along tidal water bodies or width of creek affects the livelihood security of the traditional fisher folks living within the 'No Development Zone'[2]. In accordance with the prevalence of high population, the demand for food and nutritional security increases simultaneously. The availability of aquatic resources, rich variety of fish species, tropical temperature have encouraged to exploit fisheries resources to the maximum. Fishing has emerged to be an industry reaching the world market [3]. The future of the small scale fishing community can be secured through a development process by creating an economy to protect fishing communities identity, rights and talents. Such process always should aim for generating growth, sustainable use of environment, empowerment of marginalized to bring self reliance [4].

Methodology

The study is descriptive by nature using Descriptive Research Design. Pre-tested interview schedule was used to collect data for this study from the fisher folk by conducting personal interviews to derive information about socio-demographic status, occupational details, occupational hazards, common problems, benefit schemes available to the respondents. This study was conducted in Thota Bengre village of Mangaluru Taluk, belonging to State of Karnataka in India. Based on the Marine Fisheries Census 2010, Karnataka, 731 fisher folks working as active fulltime fishers in Thota Bengre village been identified as the study population. Out of the population, 53 are selected to be the sample for the study.

Scope of Fisheries

The Fishing industry also generates income to allied sectors such as canneries, processing establishments, gear and equipment manufacturing, boat yards, refrigeration and ice making and transport services etc. It even increase the food supply thereby helps to raise the nutrition among the people. Besides being protein rich food, fishes also yields certain byproducts such

as fish oil, fish meal, fish manure, fish leather, fish glue etc.[5]. The key features such as perishable product, bulk production, consumption pattern has provided ample scope for Processing and Marketing activities. The required infrastructural support is provided by the freezing plants, canning plants, ice plants, fish meal plants, pre processing centers and cold storage. The Dakshina Kannada District with 42 km Coastal Belt comprises 27,281 fisher folk population along with 14 landing centres, 17 Fishing Villages, 4,570 fishermen families, 3,941 traditional fishermen families and 1,485 people from Below Poverty Line families. Out of total 6,139 active fishermen 3,691 engage in full time, 2,383 part timers and rest 65 engage in fish seed collection respectively. Around 1,050 Trawlers, 72 Purseseiners, 1,194 mechanised, 1,962 motorized and 57 Non Motorised boats are operating in the District [6]. In 1956, Karnataka emerged to be a Maritime State and in 1957, it established Department of Fisheries. The State comprises 300 km long coast line stretching from Majali (Karwar) in the north to Ullal (Mangalore) in the south with three coastal districts via Uttar Kannada (160kms), Udupi (98kms) and Dakshina Kannada (Mangalore Taluk 42Kms) surrounded by the Western Ghats in east and Arabian Sea in the west. Traditionally, Karnataka Coast is known as “Mackerel Coast” covering 27000sq km of Continental Shelf and 87000 sq km of Exclusive Economic Zone rich with Pelagic Fishes like sardines, mackerels etc. Dakshina Kannada district during 2011-12 and 2012-13 produced 39.57 % and 38.66 % of the total marine fish production of Karnataka.

Analysis and Interpretation

(a) Socio demographic Status: It is inferred from the analysis that majority respondents are above 46 years of age, married, having 4 dependents, living in nuclear family, having more than 16 years of work experience with primary & high school education working as skilled workers earning below Rs. 10,157 lives in the tiled house having membership with associations and food security.

(b) Occupational Profile: It is inferred that majority respondents entered this occupation in very early ages, working around 250 days in a year with 12-14 hours of work per day working as labourers in the perseseiner boats as a hereditary occupation where price is determined by auction and the contractor acting as middlemen derives more profit.

(c) Occupational Hazards: The study revealed that, majority respondents are exposed to bad habits and natural hazards and suffering from health problems like fever, acidity, abdomen pain, skin diseases, eye sight problem, hearing difficulties and body ache due to uncontrollable elements in the occupation making the profession to be hazardous in nature.

(d) Common Problems: The study reveal that, respondents are suffering with many problems including no intake of food in time, economic troubles, unfair price, heavy physical labour, inability to pay for health care, lengthy working hours and unsecure for the old age and uncertainty about accident and unemployment brings moral pressure on them.

(e) Non Beneficiaries Profile: The study revealed that, majority respondents are non beneficiaries of credit schemes, training programmes, savings schemes, legal awareness, subsidy on equipments, insurance schemes, mutual guarantee schemes, educational programmes, medical services, recreational facility, price control and housing schemes.

Recommended Suggestions

There is ample scope to increase the income of fisheries Co-operative Societies thereby improve the income of fisher folk by providing infrastructural support to adopt improved fishing and fish culture practices on scientific basis. The social, economic and political status of the fisher folk can be improved through education of the fisherfolks [7]. Reduced catches even with more efforts and unequal distribution of output value among the traditional fishermen have forced them to adopt more active fishing gear to compete with trawlers and purse seiners as a course of their effort to cope with advancement in the profession. It is inevitable for the fishermen to motorize their crafts to sustain in the competition, which force them to be indebted to the middlemen and merchants thereby loose control over the sale of their catch. It is important that, the stock holders in order to manage the fisheries resources, should work on the rights, demands, education and training of the poor fishermen in partnership with public institutions [8].

Conclusion

Sustainable growth through economic empowerment is possible by identifying job opportunities, reducing power politics at workplace, granting decision making, leadership and career enrichment [9]. It is found that, the economic development of fishery is reducing in the south west coast of India due to intensifying regional dependence on external capital, economic impoverishment, pollution of coastal waters, marine resource depletion due to over exploitative fishing [10]. The steps shall be introduced with regarding to compensation system against the losses, capital inputs, profit sharing, labour intensive employments, open access to resources to protect fishing communities from exploitations. The Fishing villages shall be provided with clean drinking water, housing, health services, infrastructural support, roads, public transport, credit facilities and other support services for storage, processing and marketing activities [11]. The marine fisheries has emerged as the important sector in the last five decades by increasing its yield both quantitatively and qualitatively shifting itself from the traditional subsistence supplementary activity to commercial activity of coastal population. Socio-economic development of the fishermen community is possible by adopting improved fishing and fish farming methods along with proper training in this regard

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